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Research Article

**MANAGEMENT AND PROGNOSTIC FACTORS OF
SQUAMOUS CELL CARCINOMA AND ADENOCARCINOMA
OF THE UTERINE CERVIX**¹Abdimazhit Munira, ¹Cheng Zhi Fang¹Gynecology department of the First Affiliated Hospital of Xinjiang Medical University 830054, Urumqi, China.

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Abstract:

To investigate the clinicopathological characteristics and survival of squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma of the cervix using Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results database. Patients with a diagnosis of squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma of the cervix were included between 2014 and 2019. Kaplan-Meier method and Cox regression models were used. A total of 189 patients were included. Of the patients with known International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics stage and tumor grade, the stage III disease was diagnosed in 42.78% patients, and 26.46.5% patients had poorly or undifferentiated histology and well differentiated are 67.72%. The 5-year cause specific survival and overall survival were 33.0% and 29.4%, respectively. In multivariate analysis, increasing age, advanced stage, and treatment by primary radiotherapy were associated with worse survival outcomes. Squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma of the cervix are rare diseases with aggressive characteristics and prone to metastasize and is dismal in prognosis. Reduced survival was associated with increasing age, advanced stage, and treatment by primary radiotherapy [1] [3].

Corresponding author:**Cheng Zhi Fang,**Gynecology department of the First Affiliated Hospital,
Xinjiang Medical University 830054, Urumqi, China.

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AIMS AND OBJECTIVE:

The aim of this research work is to examine the diagnosis and treatment of Analysis of clinicopathological features and prognostic factors of IA-II Bstage cervical cancer. Cervical cancer that is detected early is more likely to be treated successfully. Most guidelines suggest that women begin screening for cervical cancer and precancerous changes at age 21. If cervical cancer is suspected, your doctor is likely to start with a thorough examination of your cervix. A special magnifying instrument (colposcope) is used to check for abnormal cells.

INTRODUCTION:

Cervical cancer is a cancer arising from the cervix. It is due to the abnormal growth of cells that have the ability to invade or spread to other parts of the body. Early on, typically no symptoms are seen. Later symptoms may include abnormal vaginal bleeding, pelvic pain, or pain during sexual intercourse. About 90% of cervical cancer patients are squamous cell carcinoma. Adenocarcinoma of the cervix is a rare disease accounting for approximately 1-2% of uterine cervix malignancies [3].

Cervical malignant growth is a standout amongst the most well-known tumors in ladies around the world. Notwithstanding overall endeavors at screening with the point of identifying cervical disease in the beginning period, numerous malignant growths are not found until effectively progressed. Customarily, radical hysterectomy or radiation treatment alone has been acknowledged as standard treatment for beginning time obtrusive cervical malignancy, and privately propelled disease has been treated by radiotherapy alone comprising of a mix of high-portion rate intracavitary brachytherapy (ICBT) and outside bar radiotherapy (EBRT) (Coia et al, 1990; Komaki et al, 1995; Barillot et al, 1997). In the previous couple of years, significant advances in the administration of privately progressed cervical disease have been accounted for. Five randomized preliminaries demonstrated improved survival and nearby control when cisplatin-based chemotherapy was added simultaneously to radiation treatment in patients with privately progressed cervical disease (Keys et al, 1999; Morris et al, 1999; Rose et al, 1999; Whitney et al, 1999; Peters et al, 2000). This joined methodology approach delivered a flat out increment in 5-year survival of 12% as contrasted and radiation treatment alone and brought about an unexpected change in the standard of consideration for this malady. Presently that simultaneous treatment with cisplatin-based chemotherapy and radiotherapy is the standard treatment for privately progressed

cervical malignant growth, the fundamental issue in treatment is the means by which chemotherapy is utilized, very little consideration is given to the radiotherapy strategy [5] [6].

Invasive cervical cancer (ICC) ranks third as the most common malignancy and fourth as the cause of cancer-related deaths among women worldwide. Despite population-based screening and development of advanced medical treatments, the morbidity of ICC is still common in developing countries like China, yielding 132,300 new cases each year.

Currently, adenocarcinoma (ADC) receives the same standard treatments as squamous cell carcinoma (SCC): radical hysterectomy, radical hysterectomy followed by adjuvant radiotherapy (RT) or primary RT for early-stage carcinoma. Concurrent chemoradiotherapy (CCRT), which is recommended in cases of locally advanced cancer and for patients with FIGO early-stage disease, has been widely accepted and produces equivalent results. However, disparate prognoses have been observed in both SCC and ADC patients with the same stage based on FIGO guidelines. Moreover, an upward trending incidence of ADC has been reported in many countries. This upward trend is particularly evident among women under age 40. The proportion of ADC has doubled over the past decade and accounts for approximately 25% of all cases of cervical cancer. The poorer prognosis of ADC patients compared to those with SCC raises the question of whether the current standard treatment for patients with SCC is suitable for those with ADC. Thus, it is of great importance to determine the prognostic factors involved in ADC so as to establish a framework for new therapeutic strategies.

In the literature, the prognostic significance of some clinicopathological factors still remains controversial. The aim of the present retrospective study was to clarify the clinicopathological factors for predicting the prognosis for ADC and squamous cell carcinoma.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

All consecutive patients diagnosed with the FIGO staging of squamous cell carcinoma and ADC of the uterine cervix and treated at The First Affiliated Hospital of Xinjiang Medical University, China between October 2014 and January 2019 were eligible for this study retrospectively. A sum of 100 new patients with essential intrusive cervical carcinoma were treated by radiotherapy, chemotherapy and radiography at the First affiliated hospital of Xinjiang Medical University, China. Of these patients, 99.0 % had unadulterated squamous

cell carcinoma (SCC). The remaining 1 % patient with adenocarcinoma were rejected from this examination. After an underlying clinical examination, all patients experienced a total arranging workup, including a total blood tally, blood science tests, chest radiography, and biopsy of the cervical tumor. Cystoscopy and dribble implantation pyelography were performed in all patients; just in suspicious case was sigmoidoscopy performed [2] [6].

The quantities of patients are appeared by malignancy arranges in Table 1. Stages were resolved by the International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics criteria. Patients with removed metastasis (ie organize IVb cervical carcinoma) before treatment and patients treated by chemotherapy before radiation were prohibited.

Sr. No	Clinical Stage	No. of patients	% of patients
1.	Stage IB	09	9 %
2.	Stage IIA	44	44 %
3.	Stage IIB	33	33 %
4	Stage IIIA	05	5 %
5.	Stage IIIB	07	7 %
6.	Stage IVA	02	2 %
	Total	100	100 %

Table 1: Numbers of Patient by cancer staging.

Patient:

Data were obtained from the First Affiliated Hospital of Xinjiang Medical University, China between October 2014 and January 2019 that is maintained by the National Cancer Institute and consists of 18 population-based cancer registries. We included squamous cell carcinomapatients from 2014 to 2019 and permission to access research data files was obtained.

Statistical Analysis:

Factual examinations were performed with the SPSS 16.0 programming bundle (IBM, Armonk, NY). Synopsis insights are displayed as frequencies and rates. The randomization of medical clinic records was performed through the probabilistic examining process with substitution, and a test for straightforward irregular examples was utilized. The example comprised of CC patients who were conceded somewhere in the range of 2014 and 2019 and whose restorative records included histopathological or anatomopathological examinations. Deficient records or cases in which treatment was deserted before the consummation of the five-year follow-up time were barred. The season of survival was determined as the interim between the date of conclusion (by biopsy or medical procedure) in the emergency clinic record and the date of death or the finish of development. The most extreme follow-up time was five years; the instance

of any patient who stayed alive after this point was shut.

Overall survival (OS) and relapse-free survival (RFS) were obtained by the Kaplan–Meier method for different groups. **The Kaplan–Meier** estimator, also known as the product limit estimator, is a non-parametric statistic used to estimate the **survival** function from lifetime data. In our research, it is often used to measure the fraction of patients living for a certain amount of time after treatment. The log-rank test was used to compare survival curves. Variables that showed a significant association with survival were included in multivariate analysis based on the Cox proportional–hazard model. Sites of recurrence were classified as local if detected in the pelvis or vagina, and distant if detected in extrapelvic locations.

RESULT:

Patient numbers by cancer stage of the study are shown in Table 1. Mean age of the patients was 46 years (range, 18–85 years). Of the total 100 patients, the numbers of patients with stage Ib, II, and III/ IVA disease were 09, 77, and 14 respectively.

Disease-specific survival curves are shown according to cancer stages in Figure 1. The cumulative 5-year survival rates for stages Ib, II, and III/IVA disease were 93.5, 77.0, and 60.3%, respectively. [10]

Figure 1: Disease-specific survival curves for five years and ten years.

Percentage of prevalence as per the age distribution:

Percentage rates are a useful tool for comparing various characters among various populations suffering from various diseases having different

consequences. Here a detailed description has been given of the patients along with their age distribution as well as the percentage of prevalence of the diseases in various age group.

Different age parameters	Percentage of Prevalence in decades of life (%)
Age (Year)	
Median Range	46
18-30	18 %
31-40	9.52 %
41-50	15.34%
51-60	22.22%
61-70	18%
71-80	10.58%
80+ Above	6.34%

Table 2: Percentage of prevalence as per the age distribution

Differentiation of Cervical Cancer (CC) based on different stage of CC:

Patients were divided into different groups depending upon the different stages of cervical cancer they are going through in order to treat them in better way.

They were divided in various groups like well differentiated CC, moderately differentiated and poorly differentiated respectively. Their detailed percentage occurrence is given below;

Well differentiated CC	67.72 %
Moderately differentiated CC	5.82 %
Poorly/undifferentiated CC	26.46 %
TOTAL	100 %

Table 3: Differentiation of Cervical Cancer (CC) based on different stage of Lesions.

Tumor Size (T):

The letter "T" plus a number (0 to 4) describes the size and location of the tumor, including how much the tumor has grown into nearby tissues. Tumor size is measured in centimeters (cm). A centimeter is

roughly equal to the width of a standard pen or pencil. A larger tumor or a tumor that has grown more deeply into the surrounding tissue receives a higher number [9]. The details are given below;

size (cm) Parameters	3.9 (0.1-7.4)
≤4 cm	74.07 %
>4 cm	25.93 %

Table 4: Tumor size distribution.

Different Treatment options in patients of certain groups:

Most squamous cell carcinoma cases are found and treated at an early stage, when they can be removed or destroyed with local treatment methods. Small squamous cell cancers can usually be cured with these treatments. Larger squamous cell cancers are harder to treat, and fast-growing cancers have a

higher risk of coming back. In rare cases, squamous cell cancers can spread to lymph nodes or distant parts of the body. If this happens, treatments such as radiation therapy and/or chemotherapy may be needed [7] [8]. The percentage of various patients'treatment with different techniques is given in the table below;

Hysterectomy ± radiotherapy	43.92
Radiotherapy	16.93
Give up	6.35
Radiotherapy + chemotherapy	14.81
Surgical option	17.99

Table 5: Different Treatment options in patients of certain groups.

Lymphadenectomy:

No	103 (54.50)
Yes	86 (45.50)
Lymph Nodes -ve	97 (51.32)
Lymph Nodes +ve	92(48.68)

*Lymphadenectomy has no significant effects on survival outcome in patients received.

DISCUSSION:

Most of the knowledge gained during this research study was from the single-institution reports with a limited numbers of patients. Here, we identified some patients of histologically confirmed squamous cell carcinoma between different ages from the Hospitals registry. Previous studies have showed that squamous cell carcinoma accounts cervix cancers. The incidence rate in our study was 0.7%, which is lower than

previously reported. About 26.4% of squamous cell carcinoma patients have poorly or undifferentiated histology. Therefore, it is important to distinguish SCCC from poorly differentiated cervical cancer.

In this we can see that there are many patients who are suffering from cervical cancer and they get medical treatment according to their stages some patients are suffer from 1st stage of cervical cancer

and some are suffer from more than first stages they all get surgery according to their conditions and then some patients get chemotherapy if we see according to ages so we have some sample of ages between 18 to 85 age. Most of the patients consisting of 44 percent of the patients were suffering with the Stage IIA clinical stage followed by stage IIB with 33% patients. The patients were treated using various treatment options depending on their complications. Most of the patients around 44 % patients had gone through Radiotherapy along with the Hysterectomy for the recovery [12] [14].

In mostly patients the clinical symptoms are abnormal vaginal bleeding or a few of them with vaginal discharge and they get radiotherapy and chemotherapy as treatment in our data mostly patient cancer type is Squamous cell carcinoma with abnormal vaginal bleeding symptoms and after these patient there are some patient who are suffer from Papillary Squamous cell carcinoma caner type and they get treatment as surgery with chemotherapy and there clinical symptoms are contact bleeding some patients are suffering from pelvic lymph node and they also get treatment radiotherapy with chemotherapy.

According to our data the mostly patient who are suffering this cancer is falling in between 50 to 60 ages so they get treatment according to their clinical symptoms with different stages 1A 11A 1B 11B and IA1 phase 1 and phase 11 [13].

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION:

In conclusion, squamous cell carcinoma is a rare disease with aggressive characteristics and prone to metastasize and is dismal in prognosis. During this study this has been concluded that more than 95 % of the cervix patients were suffering with the squamous cell carcinoma and were treated using various techniques. Most of the patients around 44 % patients were treated with Hysterectomy & radiotherapy.Reduced survival was associated with increasing age, advanced stage, and treatment by primary radiotherapy. More studies are needed to confirm our results and develop optimal management of squamous cell carcinoma.

There are several recommendations of this study. The first is the inherent biases existing in any retrospective study. However, the major strength of the present study is the ability to describe the epidemiology, clinicopathological features, treatment trends, and survival outcomes of this rare disease using a population-based study. Second, Hospital database was with lack of information about centralized pathologic review, pathological factors

(margin status and parametrical invasion details of radiation therapy and chemotherapy, and the data of local and distant recurrence. In addition, there is little information available to guide the choice of treatment in certain patients.

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